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ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ САМОХОДНОГО ОБОРУДОВАНИЯ НА РУДНЫХ ШАХТАХ СТРАН СНГ И ЗА РУБЕЖОМ

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Аннотация: В статье рассмотрен опыт применения самоходного горного оборудования на горно-добывающих предприятиях Содружества Независимых Государств (СНГ) и дальнего зарубежья. Представлен перечень основных поставщиков самоходных машин – зарубежных компаний, специализирующихся на выпуске горной техники для шахт, рудников и карьеров по добыче полезного ископаемого.

Более подробно автором рассмотрен парк самоходного оборудования, используемого на крупнейших горно-рудных предприятиях Казахстана и России. В частности, описан опыт широкомасштабного внедрения погрузочных и доставочных машин мировых производителей самоходной техники – фирм «Sandvik Mining and Construction» (Швеция) и «Caterpillar» (США) на Жезказганском месторождении в Казахстане. Выявлено, что эксплуатация высокоэффективных и надежных машин позволила повысить производительность самоходного оборудования почти в 4,3 раза по сравнению со старой техникой.

Ключевые слова: горная техника, шахта, рудник, карьер, полезное ископаемое, самоходное оборудование, погрузочные и доставочные операции, надежность эксплуатации, производительность машин

EXPERIENCE OF USING SELF-PROPELLED EQUIPMENT IN ORE MINES OF CIS COUNTRIES AND ABROAD

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Annotation: The article considers the experience of using self-propelled mining equipment at mining enterprises of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and far abroad. The list of the main suppliers of self-propelled machines is presented – foreign companies specializing in the production of mining equipment for mines, mines and quarries for the extraction of mineral resources.

The author discussed in more detail the fleet of self-propelled equipment used at the largest mining enterprises in Kazakhstan and Russia. In particular, the experience of large-scale introduction of loading and delivery machines of world manufacturers of self-propelled equipment – companies "Sandvik Mining and Construction" (Sweden) and "Caterpillar" (USA) at Zhezkazgan field in Kazakhstan is described. It was revealed that the operation of highly efficient and reliable machines allowed to increase the productivity of self-propelled equipment by almost 4.3 times compared to old equipment.

Keywords: mountain equipment, mine, mine, pit, mineral, self-propelled equipment, loading and delivery operations, operation nedezhnost, performance of cars

Today, the development of mineral deposits using self-propelled mining equipment (SGO) is characteristic of many of the world's largest mining enterprises: in North America – «Henderson Mine, Colorado», «Aj Project, Alaska» (USA); «David Bell Mine, Ontario», «Trout Lake Mine, Manitoba» (Canada); in South America – "El Indio Mine" (Chile); in Africa – «Premier Diamond Mine» (South Africa); «ZCCM» (Zambia); in Europe – "Tara Mines" (Ireland); "Kiryna" (Sweden) et al.

The main suppliers of self-propelled mining equipment are such well-known companies as «Sandvik Mining and Construction» and «Atlas Copco» (Sweden), «Caterpillar» and «Vagner» (USA), «Hitachi» (Japan), as well as a number of German, Finnish and French firms [1, 2].

The number of machine sizes and models produced by world manufacturers of self-propelled mining machinery is quite large, so that consumers have the opportunity from a very wide range of machines produced to choose for any specific mining and geological conditions such a model that most corresponds to them.

Figure 1 shows a number of models of self-propelled mining equipment produced by one of the world leaders in the supply of mechanisms, equipment and tools for the mining and construction industries – the «Sandvik Mining and Construction» campaign (Sweden).

The campaign was formed in 1998 by combining the Finnish company «Tamrock» with the Swedish campaign «Sandvik Rock Tools».

In the CIS countries, in particular in Kazakhstan and Russia, self-propelled equipment was most widely used in the mining industry in the extraction of ores of ferrous and non-ferrous metals, mining and chemical raw materials.

Achieving the necessary volumes of underground mining at ore mines required the active introduction of expensive self-propelled equipment of the above-mentioned leading world producers, which has high productivity and reliability in operation.

Over the past 25 years, mining enterprises of the countries of the former Union have practically updated the entire range of self-propelled vehicles used.

At the ore mines of «Apatit» OJSC (Russia), the world's largest producer of phosphate raw materials, almost the entire fleet of self-propelled equipment was replaced in the late 1990s. By acquiring modern self-propelled machines, ensuring the high quality of their maintenance and repair, the company managed to significantly increase production efficiency.

In particular, at the United Kirov Mine, the largest of the 4 mines of «Apatit» OJSC, which uses a system with underfloor forced collapse with an area release of ore to loading rides to work out the horizons, various types of self-propelled equipment are widely used.

Figure 1 – Model range of self-propelled mining equipment manufactured by «Sandvik Mining and Construction» (Sweden)
 a – "Toro 40D"; b – "Toro 50 +"; c – «Toro 301DL»; d – "Toro 400"; e – «Minimatic»; f – «Robot»

Currently, the mine uses: for penetration of workings – drilling machines "Minimatic 205-40», loading and delivery machines (PDM) of the type "Toro 007" and "Toro 400" (figure 1, d), underground car dump trucks "Toro 35" (manufacturer – company " Sandvik Mining and Construction». The auxiliary machines at the mine are represented by two foreign suppliers:

– "Normet" company (Finland) – "Multimec" cassette systems, "Spraymec" shotcreting units, "Skaimec" depopulation units;
– «Paus» (Germany): Unifers charging machines, machines for delivering people to «Mink 18» mining plants, etc. [3-5].

At the Oryol mine of the Zhezkent Mining and Processing Plant (Kazakhstan), which uses a descending layer development system with the laying of the developed space with hardening mixtures, «Caterpillar» loading and delivery machines – R1300LHD and «Sandvik Mining and Construction» – «Toro 301DL» were widely used to deliver ore from treatment and mining slabs.

Drilling carriages "Minibur G1F" are used for drilling holes during penetration of preparatory-rifled workings and development of approaches. As the experience of operation of foreign equipment has shown, with high efficiency of using self-propelled equipment, it is possible to increase labor productivity by 2-4 times and reduce production costs by 20-50% [6].

At the enterprises of Kazakhmys Corporation, developing the Zhezkazgan field (Kazakhstan), starting in the mid 90s. last century, a large-scale introduction of new equipment began. In 1996-1997 60 units of "Toro 40D" car dump trucks were purchased and commissioned (Figure 1, a), with a carrying capacity of 40 tons, which completely replaced the «МоА3-7405» in cleaning operations.

At the same time, the productivity of the new machine with an average age of 2.6 years increased 4.3 times compared to the «МоА3-7405» at the age of 2.1 years, and 1.7 times due to better use (organizational measures) and 2.5 times due to technical productivity. «Caterpillar» machines are successfully used for ore loading and export at treatment works: "Cat 980C; F; G", which secured the position of a reliable and operable loader in difficult conditions.

Loading and delivery machines "Toro 501DL" were put into operation at the mining workings for loading and delivery operations, the annual productivity of which exceeded the best performance of the previously operated PNB loading machine by 2.1 times. For drilling in the treatment face and at the penetration of the workings, Kazakhmys Corporation made a transition from pneumatic units «УБИШ» and «СБУ» to hydraulic two-boom "Paramatic, H205T 205-90", "Axera – D05" and "Monomatic 105-40" (all units are the model range of «Sandvik Mining and Construction»).

Thus, it can be stated that the variety of mining-geological and mining-technical conditions in which self-propelled equipment is operated has led manufacturers to produce a large number of types and models of machines designed for efficient operation under certain conditions (table 1).

Table 1 – Nomenclature and basic technical data of self-propelled mining equipment

Brand (model)	Power, kw	Weight, tons	Dimensions, millimeters					Rotation radius, millimeters/degrees		Quantity driving bridges	Capacity, tons	Capacity bucket (bodies) m ³	Maximum speed, km/h
			length	width	height	to the front bridge	between bridges	external	internal				
Shelves for roofing in cleaning faces													
«CFL-18A»	132	15,63	13000	2600	3900	1299	3950	-	-	1	-	60	
«CFL-8E»	132	16,0	10500	2600	2900	1299	3950	-	-	1	-	60	
«CFL-8A»	132	15,7	8200	2600	2900	1299	3950	-	-	1	-	60	
«CFL-18E»	132	15,7	9440	2600	2900	1299	3950	-	-	1	-	60	
Self-propelled loading and load-haul-dumpers													
«Toro 650»													
«Toro 501»	261	38,2	11066	3300	3200	3696	3770	7366	3297	2	15,0	6,0	26
ILI-2B	242	36,7	10680	2710	2850	3360	3500	7500	-	2	14,0	7,0	25
«MoA3-55	55	10,15	7100	1600	1870	1780	2930	-	-	2	3,0	0,8	18
4053»	220	3,7	9960	2637	2300	3558	3537	6700	3100	2	9,0	6,5	-
«LK-1ACD»	102	13,5	8335	2340	2050	-	3300	5990	3100	2	4,0	2,0	13,3
«Cat-980G»	224	29247	9500	3200	3150	2493	3700	7780	-	2	14,0	5,3	37
Mine dump trucks													
«Toro 40D»	335	28,5	10036	3036	2687	3235	5296	9000	4944	2	40	22	40
«MoA3-7405»	140	19,5	8610	2860	2610	2960	4450	7600	3500	2	22	14	40
«Cat-3408E»	365	41,8	10660	3000	2700	3390	5550	9195	5259	2	40	21,3	45
Charging and delivery machines													
«IM3III»	132	15,7	8950	2600	2900	1299	3950	-	-	1	0,6	-	60
«MA-2»	10,6	8,5	8000	1600	1800	2350	2450	-	-	1	-	-	-
Self-propelled drilling rigs													
«CIII-250»	392	70	9200	5450	15450	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,77
«YIII 312A»	-	15,5	12000	2000	2500	-	-	/6	/3,2	-	-	-	10
«YIII 227»	-	6,1	7600	1300	1650	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,8
«P1500»	250	18	9700	2490	3100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
«Ranger 7»	145	13,7	7100	2450	3600	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The study of the experience of introducing self-propelled equipment at the mining enterprises of the CIS shows that equipment of operations of technological process of production of the mining enterprises by modern highly effective self-propelled cars and means of mechanization allowed to lift the performance of underground mines to new level and today production is faced by not less difficult task – receiving return from huge investments into re-equipment, reduced costs for operation of expensive machines due to increased efficiency of use and resource saving [7, 8].

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